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Dr. Sachin Napate obtained his B.A. (Eco) from Bombay University, MBA (Finance) and PhD from S.R.T.M.U.Nanded. He has published two books on "Term of the Day" and "Wealth Management" at National Library, Singapore. He has been contributing articles to various national and international journals. He is a Professor (Finance) at Business School in Pune, approved by AICTE. He had 14 years of industry experience and has been associated with the academics over 11 years. Beside this, he has deep interest in various aspect of financial consultancy, case-analysis workshop, team-building, etc.

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